

A Research Paper on Introduction of Psychology in Industry

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Abstract

When you learn what industrial organizational psychologists study, you'll understand why this branch of psychology is important. You might even decide to choose this specialty when earning your psychology degree or choosing a job! Industrial-organizational psychology studies how individuals behave and cooperate in work settings. Social psychology studies how the behavior of people is influenced by the presence or opinion of others (Kuther & Morgan, 2012). Bachelor's, master's, and doctoral degree holders' are offered many employment opportunities due to the high applicability of these spheres of psychology. The practical value of industrial-organizational and social psychology may be explained by the fact that human behavior determines everything that is connected with communication and work performance.

Keywords:

Industrial Psychology, healthy work environment, Mental Health, Human Relations

Introduction:

Industrial psychologists apply the theories and principles of psychology to the workplace in an attempt to "enhance the dignity and performance of human beings, and the organizations they work in, by advancing the science and knowledge of human behavior" (Rucci, 2008, p. 17).

In turn, a practitioner adopts various principles and theories, including (Aamodt, 2010):

- *Social learning theory* to build training and development programs and incentive plans
- *Social psychology* to create working groups to understand and reduce employee conflict
- *Motivational and emotional theories* to meet the psychological needs of employees and increase their satisfaction at work

While industrial psychologists are engaged in areas similar to human resource managers, they often differ in techniques and rationale. For example, industrial psychologists rely on psychological testing, behavioral interviews, and work data. On the other hand, human resources departments typically adopt unstructured interviews to progress staff selection and promotion (Aamodt, 2010).

The Importance Of Industrial Psychology In The Workplace:

A person considering a degree or career in psychology may wonder, "Why is industrial-organizational psychology important?" While other specialties of psychology delve into a particular person's personality and mental health issues that they are facing, industrial

and organizational psychology (IO) takes a somewhat different approach. IO psychology professionals assess and improve individual, group, and organizational dynamics in the work environment. They can recommend strategies to improve organizational structure and human relations. They use their training in psychological principles to create:

- a healthy work environment
- increase employee satisfaction
- develop new employee training

Having a psychology professional in the organization can also improve employee productivity. When you learn what industrial organizational psychologists study, you'll understand why this branch of psychology is important. You might even decide to choose this specialty when earning your psychology degree or choosing a job!

Nature Of Industrial Psychology:

Mr. Arthur Stephenson, of the National Institute of Industrial Psychology, read a paper on some observations on accidents in industry. Although one must not belittle the success of mechanical safeguards, yet 90 per cent. of present-day accidents are to be accounted for as failures on the part of the human subject. The U.S. Federal Board for Vocational Education gives many examples of efficient safety work in various industries, but only one-third of the reductions in the personnel sustaining accidents has been effected by mechanical safeguards : two-thirds have been accomplished through organisation and education. Mr. Davis, Secretary of Labour, states that the fatal industrial accidents in the U.S.A. probably

exceed 23,000 per annum and non-fatal accidents 2f millions, and he is advised by experts that 85 per cent. of these are preventable. In Great Britain there are about 1200 fatal accidents per annum in factories and workshops, and another 1200 in coal mines and quarries. Non-fatal accidents of sufficient severity to cause disablement for a week or more number 120,000 a year in factories, and 200,000 a year in coal mines. The National Institute of Industrial Psychology, so NO.

The National Institute of Industrial Psychology, sofar back as 1922, recommended preliminary surface instruction of youths entering the mine and applied a scheme of training. Mr. Stephenson described an experiment where learners were trained in an industrial process along certain lines. Some of the learners were raw novices while others had had previous experience. Periodical tests of efficiency were made and those who proved incapable of profiting by instructions were discharged. After the scheme had been in operation for 10 months the accident frequency was analysed. The frequency rate for novices dismissed was 10 times as great as for novices retained, while for experienced learners dismissed it was 3! times as great as for experienced learners retained. The data obtained made it probable that ability to acquire the neuro-muscular coordination required by the particular process, is at least as important a factor as age or experience. Whilst agreeing that a considerable advance may be made by educational and propaganda methods, it is considered probable that the scientific selection of the workers would probably tend to diminish the frequency rate of accidents.

2. Miss W. Spielman gave a lecture on recent progress in vocational selection. The older methods of vocational selection were compared with modern methods employing mental and physical tests. This lecture served as an introduction to the demonstration given at the conversazione, by Miss Spielman and her assistants, of psychological tests in use at the National Institute of Industrial Psychology. There were tests for vocational guidance (e.g. of intelligence, mechanical ability, and manual dexterity) ; and tests for vocational selection (e.g. for engaging weavers, packers, clerks, sales assistants, etc.). In addition, the material collected from various countries by

the Research Committee on Vocational Guidance was on view and the various reports of this Committee were distributed to those interested.

3. Mr. Eric Farmer, investigator to the Industrial Fatigue Research Board, arranged an exhibition, and gave a demonstration at the conversazione, of apparatus designed for the Board by Dr. Schuster, namely, a pursuit-meter, steadiness-meter, a fatigueinducing apparatus, a dotting apparatus, an original type of chronoscope for serial reactions, and a figuresetting apparatus which serves excellently as a non-verbal test of intelligence. All were original in design and ingenious in workmanship and well calculated to render effective service in the hands of the industrial psychologist

A brief history of the field

Early in the 20th century, when the field of psychology was still very new, a few psychologists turned their attention to work behavior. Prior to the First World War, Hugo Munsterberg began working on improving staff selection for streetcar operators. At the same time, Walter Dill Scott, a pioneer of industrial psychology, studied salespersons and the psychology of advertising (Riggio, 2017).

Frederick Taylor, an engineer, suggested using science to understand work behavior. He became the founder of the scientific management movement and the originator of time-and-motion studies, successfully improving the efficiency of many manual roles and tasks.

However, more complex, modern tasks are less suited to the approach, as they can be performed in multiple ways depending on the context and desired outcome, such as computer coding, marketing, or design (Riggio, 2017).

It wasn't until after the Second World War that industrial psychology received more widespread attention, pushed along by legislation changes, such as the Civil Rights Act of 1964.

By the 2000s, the most significant change to employees and industrial psychologists was the rapid rise and advances in technology, particularly the speed and volume of communication and the ability to connect with anyone worldwide instantly (Aamodt, 2010).

Today, “industrial/organizational psychology is one of the fastest growing areas of psychology” (Riggio, 2017, p. 13).

The six scopes of industrial psychology

- 1. Economic, Social and Psychological Aspect.
- 2. Study of the Physical Aspect of Work Environment.
- 3. Principles of Human Relationships .
- 4. Study of Aptitudes and Motives .
- 5. Study of Principles of Mental Health of the Industry .
- 6. Study of Human Relation.

1. Economic, Social and Psychological Aspect of the Industry:

Industrial psychology deals with human behavior in the entire industrial environment. Consequently, it studies the economic, social and psychological aspects of human behaviour. In the modern age most of economic factors have some psychological influence. The various factors in communal life of workers living in industrial environment also influence the psychology of the worker. Industrial psychology studies these factors.

2. Study of the Physical Aspect of Work Environment:

In an industry the worker is greatly influenced by the working conditions. If the conditions are well, the worker feels satisfied and remains healthy while on the other hand if the conditions are not good the workers become dissatisfied. Industrial psychology deals with the physical working conditions.

3. Principles of Human Relationships:

Irrespective of the automation introduced in industries, the human element can not be eliminated. Even most efficient machine needs an engineer to run it, and because the engineer is a human being the most importance of the psychological element in the running of the factory cannot be ignored. The efficiency of the human being will depend very much upon the nature of his relations with the management.

In the previous century most industrialists behaved like autocrats and considered the workers as nothing more than tools. But in

that period the efficiency level was not very high.

It has been seen that an industrialist can achieve a higher rate of production if he behaves sympathetically with his employees. An industrialist who cannot maintain good relations with his workers does not succeed for long time. Industrial psychology tries to discover principles for improving human relationships in an industrial environment.

4. Study of Aptitudes and Motives:

As in any other circumstances, human behaviour in the industrial environment is influenced and formed by attitudes and aims. Behaviour changes with the changes in stimuli. Hence it is very important to study the rules pertaining to correct attitudes and aims.

Industrial psychology pursues this kind of study. An important example of study of this kind is the study conducted by Hawthorne Works Western Electric Company into the effect of the attitudes of workers upon production. This study is known as the Hawthorne Study.

5. Study of Principles of Mental Health:

Today all intelligent people realize the importance of maintaining the proper health of workers. The workers mental health is influenced by working conditions and by the attitude of other people towards him. Industrial psychology not only studies the factors influencing the mental health of industrial workers but also tries to discover principles for maintaining their mental health. Industrial “psychology also gives

suggestions for improving the mental health of those who are suffering from mental disease or are otherwise unbalanced.

6. Study of Human Relation:

Industrial psychology is the study of human behaviour in an industrial context. Being a branch of psychology, industrial psychology is particularly concerned with the observation

What do Industrial Organizational Psychologists Do?

By using human psychology principles to study behavior in a place of work, industrial psychology professionals can determine:

- how well teams communicate
- whether or not workers are invested in the company
- overall job satisfaction
- improve employee productivity

All these factors contribute to an employee's productivity, efficiency, and absenteeism rate. These are important because they directly impact an organization's bottom line and its ability to meet deliverables. The importance of industrial psychology is largely rooted in these practitioners' ability to:

- quickly assess a company
- identify barriers to productivity and efficiency
- develop a plan to remedy those problems

Industrial psychology also uses psychological principles to develop evidence-based procedures for:

- hiring
- training employees
- retention

Essentially, the field consists of conducting research into workplace dynamics and applying research findings to optimize business efficiency and employee satisfaction in the work environment.

It's important to note that the one-on-one work that an industrial-organizational

psychologist may do is very different from the one-on-one work done by a traditional psychologist. IO psychologists are not trained in diagnosing mental disorders, and they don't dig deep into the psyche of a worker or manager. Rather, they evaluate personality traits and human behavior as they pertain to the person's work.

While most industrial-organizational psychologists focus on the work environment, the specialty of industrial psychology doesn't necessarily have to be connected to work in the traditional sense — it can be applied to any type of purpose-driven activity. An industrial psychologist can be very helpful to sports teams and volunteer efforts as well.

CHALLENGES: Before proceeding to the methods and content of industrial psychology it might be best to mention certain major problems which the profession has to face in its future growth and development.

1. The Consultant and the Staff Psychologist:

A psychologist directly employed full time by a company or by a government agency is often refined to as a "staff" psychologist. Generally speaking, the duties and tasks of the consultant and the staff psychologist overlap. There is no clear-cut difference insofar as type of assignment is concerned. The major difference is that the consultant may be concurrently working for a number of

clients or employers, whereas the staff psychologist fills a more specific role in the

organization chart for a single employer.

Although a schism between the staff psychologist and the consultant is undesirable if the profession is to be advanced in industry, the answers given in Canters study (1948) to the question "What do you think of consulting firms as the best solution to industrial psychological problems?" pose a serious future problem. One-half of the staff psychologist group was unfavourable toward such firms; the consulting group was generally favourable. This situation demands attention and should be cleared up.

A note of optimism is reflected toward the field in general since 80 percent of the respondents reported that executives were becoming more "psychological minded". A further indication of the increased acceptance of the psychologist by leaders in industry comes from a 1962 survey conducted by Feinberg and Lefkowitz (1962).

They administered a questionnaire to 89 executives who were attending a seminar sponsored by the American Management Association. When asked whether they would be interested in hiring an industrial psychologist, over two thirds replied favourably.

These "yes" respondents felt the industrial psychologist could be of greatest benefit in the areas of employee motivation, employee selection and training, executive selection and training, human engineering, consumer

research, production efficiency, and accident control.

2. Communication:

One of the difficulties of any profession is that its language and technique sometimes become so involved that the outsider is really left out. If industrial psychology is to gain an important place in industry, psychologists must learn to talk and write in a fashion that is clearly understandable to others who are equally interested in the mutual problems and who sometimes have an even greater stake in a solution. Not only must the industrial psychologist learn to communicate adequately with the non-psychologist, but even the problem of communication within the field itself is becoming a problem.

The ever-increasing complexity of industrial psychology and the specialization of interest of the psychologists working on different problems in different settings has created many barriers to the flow and dissemination of knowledge among researchers and practitioners. While such problems may be the inevitable corollary of a dynamic discipline, the authors feel that the communication problem is one of the most critical in industrial psychology today.

3. Resistance to Change:

Research findings as well as research itself can ordinarily be expected to meet with resistance on the part of employees and, in many instances, employers. The successful

practitioner of industrial psychology must be immediately and forever aware of this phenomenon. It would be purely academic if one anticipated that industry is waiting with open arms to apply the knowledge of industrial psychology.

Attempts at change, no matter how well-intentioned, produce threats and will be

What Types of Research do Industrial Psychology Professionals Do?

The types of research used in industrial psychology vary widely. Industrial psychology professionals may:

- primarily conduct observational research
- design and carry out studies
- use surveys

Most use a combination of different research methods. Because industrial psychologists are trained as both researchers and practitioners, most people in this field both conduct research and apply it. However, some industrial psychology experts (mostly those working in academia) may focus purely on research. Others focus purely on the application of that research.

IO psychologists conduct research to draw conclusions that allow them to better help businesses achieve their goals. Some examples include:

- developing personality assessments that help businesses select the most suitable employees
- evaluating employee training programs to ensure they meet company objectives
- conducting observational research where they monitor several different businesses to see which management strategies work best and why.

Conclusion:

If you want a career that makes a positive difference in human behavior in the workplace, IO psychology might be right for you! The industrial organizational psychologists definition according to the APA is a psychologist whose role is to study “human behavior in the work environment and applies general psychological principles to work-related

resisted. This resistance may take the form of hostility and aggression against the change itself or against the administrator of the projected change. Often the employee imagines the nature of the change well in advance of the possibility of a change.

issues and problems.” As an IO psychologist, you’ll strive to improve areas like:

- Personnel selection
- Personnel training
- Employee evaluation
- Working conditions
- Accident prevention
- Job analysis
- Job satisfaction
- Leadership
- Team effectiveness
- Work motivation

These are the rewarding job functions of an industrial psychology professional. Knowing, “Why is industrial-organizational psychology important?” could also help a person promote the profession and explain to others exactly what it is that they do in their job.

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